

RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN PROJECT RISK MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND CLIENT SATISFACTION: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

¹**Hammed, Olawale Gazal**

Department of Management Technology, Faculty of Management Sciences,
Lagos State University, OJO, Lagos Nigeria

Email: olawale.hammed@lasu.edu.ng ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000000349839916>

²**Shofoluwe, A, Musibau**

Department of Built Environment, College of Science & Technology,
North Carolina A & T State University Greensboro, NC27411, U.S.A

Email: musibaas@ncat.edu ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000000207133581>

³**Njogo, Bibiana**

Department of Management Accounting, College of Management Sciences,
Bells University of Technology, Ota Ogun state, Nigeria

Email: bibiananjogo@yahoo.com ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000000322033500>

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ABSTRACT

Aim of the Study: This paper tends to evaluate the relationship between certain construction project risk management practices and client satisfaction.

Design/Methodology: Survey research design was adopted for this study with the aids of structured questionnaire, for collection of data from a stratified random sample of 46 project managers of the participating construction firms and 230 clients of those firms respectively, which are registered with Lagos Chamber of Commerce. Linear regression analysis was used for the data analysis.

Findings: The findings of the result revealed that, there was a significant relationship ($R = 0.580$; $p < 0.05$) between project risk management practices and client satisfaction. From the findings of the study, this study shows that incorporating those feedbacks, through checklist, mandatory and reporting forms as risk management process into organization planning process would enhance client satisfaction.

Practical Implications: The study recommended among others that Identification and management of risk should be part of an acceptable and functioning of quality and cost management strategy of the firm, based on the links between these variables as they complement each other.

Originality/value: The study has contributed to existing literatures by establishing significant relationships between project risk, and client satisfaction and further show the accounts in variation of clients' satisfaction, when the practices are effectively managed.

Key words; Risk management Client satisfaction, Risk identification, Risk mitigation and Risk response

Paper Type: Research Article

1. INTRODUCTION

Risk is an integral part of any business in which construction industry is not immune from this various potential risks due to the nature and complexities of the project (Hammed,2021). Therefore, managing risk is essential to construction project due to the fact that use to identify the potential risk and provide the means to mitigate the effect of the risk associated with building a project. (Fatemah, et. al.,2020). Project manager are considered to be a key player in managing risk in construction project through proper planning and systematic techniques that requires both knowledge and experience documented from previous project. This will enable unexpected circumstances that could hinder the carrying out the project goal to be identified and profound a corrective measure (Serpella, et. al. 2014).

In the study of (Hammed 2021) it was stated that initiatives completed in the building industry are highly complicated with substantial spending. Project managers are saddled with the responsibility of the associated risk that are capable of influencing outcomes project negatively. Managing risk is considered to be a proactive measure as against a reactive concept, because it involves a proper planning that raise the possibility of acquiring project's accomplishment.

From the perspective of building sector, it could be deduced that risk management are mainly concerns with managing construction risk of their project, which are associated with the construction activities and allocation of resources for the construction project. These are used to identify and lessen the effects of such risks influence the objective and the overall goal of a project negatively project (Naseer et. al, 2021). Globally construction firms are referring to as one of the most precarious and challenging industries. The industry is sometimes view as weak in reputation, when it comes to managing risk, due to delay in project delivery and cost overrun (Hwang, 2017).

The foundation of contemporary nations' prosperity is their construction sector. Due to the global increase in demand for infrastructure and amenities, there has been a rapid development in the economy. The basic conditions of living are provided by construction industry, which makes construction industry to be refer to as the pillar of modern country success because it promotes a sustainable and development environment for humans' life. In order to achieve this, different types of risk are encountered by the project due to rapid increase of population and growing economic activities.

Risk is more prevalent in construction project; therefore, it is not possible to experience or record zero. Nature of risk in construction industry is inherent because of its inability to sometimes achieve budget, quality and schedule triple constraints of construction activities. Complexity of construction project made is outcome to more unpredictable. The uncertain events are capable of influencing the overall goal of project negatively. Project risk management could be a better

approach of ensuring superior quality, on schedule, adequate budget and environmental sustainability of project objective. It has been observed that attention are more directed on certain area of risk control in building projects. The holistic approach with comprehensive focus on the extent to which certain variables identified could impact the overall objectives has been neglected, especially in a developing economy like Nigeria. As compared with other industries the risk and uncertainties in this sector are very high because of complex nature of its activities. In the study of (Fatemah et al 2020). It was stated that time, quality and cost are the major constraints of construction industry in Nigeria Project management is a distinct task that calls for distinct knowledge and abilities. (Kerzner 2018), explained that important things to think about for project success in building projects are project oversight knowledge and skills. This implies that various aspect of construction project required adequate skills and knowledge of risk associated project accomplishment Despite these writers' substantial contributions, most of these challenges still persist. This raises a concern to conduct a study on relationships between project risk management practices and client satisfaction.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Preamble

Tohidi (2011) described project risk management is a procedure that involves determining and mitigating risk, using an appropriate risk technique to reduce potential risk capable of influencing outcome of project negatively to a barest minimum. In the study of (Smith 2014) risks in construction project were categorized into three main divisions, which are unknown unknown, known known, unknown known risk. The decreasing ability to predict or foreseen risks is the major difference between these various categories of risk. (Lawrence 2015) stated that likelihood of a hazardous incident and its consequence on the goals of the project are subject of risk management. Risk events are viewed as part of construction activities that could impacts project cost, quality and timely delivery of a project which could influence the overall goal of a project. Some of these risks could also be emanated external factors such as social, political, administrative and environmental factors (Fatemah, et al ,2020). (Oguzhan 2020) viewed categorization of risk in construction as probability of occurrence, controllability and extent of its impact.

2.2 Project Risk Management Process

Earlier literatures revealed widespread of risk assortment that arises from erection of buildings and several methods of managing risk which are permitted to control possible hazards. Many studies have demonstrated certain thought from their review, which has brought out viewing risk management as a proactive measure in construction industry (Divya et.al. 2022). (Ahmadi, et. al. 2017) stated that risk management has become a popular concept to most construction firms. Most construction firms do consider implementation of risk management to improve their project success and enhance productivity of their firm. (Aven 2016) explained that risk management received much attention because it was viewed as the techniques of improving schedule, cost, and technical success of a project. Risk and

uncertainty are sometimes used interchangeably but there different. In construction project uncertainty is viewed as one of the risk factors that is highly important, which is consider to be a random event with unknown probability is among the most significant risk factors for initiatives that have the potential to be random events with uncertain probabilities. The approach that involves understanding project goal and establishing the process to achieve its benefits are considered as Project risk management and this also consider data and strategies to compute project risk information. Tools such as Monte Carlo modeling, stochastic predominance, Methods for Program Assessment and Review, Probability Network Evaluation Technique and Narrow Reliability Bounds are used quantify risk in approach to risk management.

The approach of effective risk management for projects has been practiced by professionals in project management field and this has sometimes promoted success of their project. During execution stage of a project, project risk management could be used as an instrument of value to mitigates the effects of risk capable of influencing outcome of project negatively. Moreso, it is sometimes used to manage project and determine the value for general business. (Oguzhan, 2020).

Project manager needs project risk control to guarantee project accomplishment. It is also known as one of the project management knowledge domains that aims to reduce damage, loss, minimize cost, control and limits effect of risk on specification (PMI, 2016).

(Hilson 2003) quoted in the publication of (Hammed 2021) categorized risk as been dynamic and static. The study further classified project risk management plan as determining the danger, Risk evaluation, risk monitoring, as well as risk reduction that that effective project risk managers treat risk management as a dynamic part of every project.

2.3 Dynamic Risk and Static Risk

(Baloj et. al. 2003) also categorized risk as static and dynamic risk. Static risk was viewed as potential loss encountered by people that can only be minimized by risk aversion, while Dynamic risk envisage both potential loss and gain simultaneously. The approach of managing risk can put the overall goal of a project because most risk are vivacious in nature because making opportunities could be concerned with developing new and innovative product, which could be to risk loss for something certain and gain for uncertainty.

2.4 Sources of Risk

Risk is often encountered through various sources. Some of the source rages from technological risk, financial risk, construction risk and environmental risk etc. Most of these sources of risk are viewed as product- particular and non-product- certain hazards, managing risk, these kinds of danger are very important to project success. The project team has to assist an organization establish metrics to determine this source of risk and break it down to element that could be more detailed and measured... This would enable easy identification and understanding of the potential risk to those saddled with the responsibility of managing the risk of the undertaking. It's a challenging to divide element of danger in to various source because of its potentials for

subjectivity. This can bring about "double-counting" because some risk could be attributed to more than one source. (Lawrence, 2015).

2.5 Project Risk Management in Construction Project

Due to excessive level of variability in projects, Managing risks is mostly used to monitor and manage danger in a systemic arrangement that allows proper risk identification and proffer a solution to mitigate its impact. Observation and lesson learnt from previous executed projects have become among the principal techniques for risk identification in building projects. During planning and contracting of project work, risk management process ought to have commenced along with the exploratory and capital budgets, which also corroborate with early phase of project initiation. Later stages of risk management are applied rationally in subsequent phases, with essential components that aids the control of negative outcome of project success. Initial warning are made to project manager from the potential threats previously identified to track the project's result, listed in order not to deviate from the expected goal of the project. (Cleland et. al, 2006).

There are four important phases in construction mechanism. Planning, programming, procurement and production are the essential phases. The customer gets an idea of the project and researches from the programming phase, while at planning stage, client attest to construction drawing develops in accordance with their requirement by an architect. Procurement phase involves all parties signing contractual agreement needed for the project. The contractors embarked on activities needed for the execution of the project at the production phase. Time, cost and quality are viewed as one of the major danger elements in building projects that are capable of influencing outcome of construction project negatively. Project manager are to be aware and prepared in advance for the potential risk using an effective risk identification technique.

Irrespective of project size and capacity, there different types of risk to be encountered in construction industry. Construction project do experienced differentiation in the design and scope, coupled with project completion time frames, these are most prevalent risk in construction industry. Variation in resources, duration and budget occurs, when there is change in procedure for the project design or capacity for the project execution. Trouble could also be emanated from completion of project before the expected competition of project and not just from time overrun alone. Inadequate planning or inappropriate design might be the cause of completion ahead of expected time for completion of the project. which in reality could leads to poor quality of the deliverables or cost overrun of the project. (Mohammed et. al. 2018)

2.6 Project Risk Management and Performance of Construction Industry

(Adeleke et. al. 2018) investigated the methods of risk management affected the outcome of projects. The aim of their investigation is to assess how widely techniques for risk management are used in Brazilian companies. The results indicate that putting risk management into practice techniques greatly enhances the project performance. Additionally, they demonstrate how having A risk manager possesses a favorable effect on the accomplishment of the project.

An analysis of earlier research found a high association between building project's effectiveness as well as risk supervision. "A higher risk may result in a higher gain" is said. The results of initiatives will be enhanced by minimizing hazards. The way a building project performs in terms of cost, schedule, and excellence is greatly influenced by dangers. The ability In order to control hazards during the construction process, grown essential to preventing unexpected consequences due to the scale and complexity of projects expanded. Furthermore, Risk mitigation is recognized is an essential practice to improve how well construction projects are doing. A building initiatives ability to fulfill its objectives in terms of schedule, money, quality, safety, and environmental sustainability is a crucial sign of success. (Chang, et. al, 2018)

2.7 Theoretical Frame Work

Outcomes of decision-making process could have been ideally predictable but based on condition of uncertainty and risk, most construction projects rarely go according to plan. The intuit and rational of decision makers to assess the degree of certainty and probability of factors that could influence, whether an event could take place have subject a decision to be a condition of under risk. Person experience and data available past similar project are also important in making decisions while facing danger. (Ceric, 2003).

In Making decisions when there is danger, expected value was one theory earliest theory propounded. Model of expected value theory didn't consider that monetary worth of an individual does not directly relate to its particular payoff value. Systematic bias in decision-making was introduce by Bernoulli as a concept. The concept presumed that individual does not really bother about their expected value as compared with how they tend to maximize their utilities. Also, there is a subjective utility model created by Morgenstern and Von Neumann, which assume that same utility curve might not be shared by different people, but each despite that everyone one defined their maximum subjective utility that follows same normative structure (Tversky & Kahneman, 1979).

Decision-making under conditions of risk is one of the major assumptions of prospect theory. Trade-offs of value is one of the decisions in internal conflict resolution. World of uncertainty was better explained, described and typically predict by prospect theory. The decision-making process are evaluated and frame on how this theory addressed choice of individual. Domains of loss and gains have different utility curve as presumed by prospect theory. Common pattern of choice was explained based on how the theory was design with both descriptive and empirical in analysis. There are two phases of decision making in prospect theory namely: framing and evaluation phases. Manner at which a decision maker makes their choice based on their personal discretion is referred to as framing, while evaluation phase is divided in to two parts in prospect theory. These are weighting function and value function. In prospect theory value function is defined as a absolute wealth but rather reference point related to gain and loss of value. It is described in form of change with reference to starting point to determine whether the change could be positive or negative. (Lawrence, 2015).

The domain of risk propensity could be predicted using prospect theory approach. Gains has less emotional equivalent impact compared with losses that has higher impact, therefore in decision making loss weighted more heavily. Decision weight are always multiplied with each value of the outcome by the decision makers. Empirically generated decision weights evaluate how individuals truly arrive at their likelihood perception and not just solely serve as a measure of perceived likelihood of an outcome. High and medium probabilities are subjectively underweighted, while low probabilities are overweight (Lawrence, 2015).

3. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The primary goal because of this research was to evaluate the relationships between project procedures for risk oversight and client satisfaction

Research Question

To what extent does project risk management practices enhance clients' satisfaction?

4. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

Ho: Project risk management practices do not enhance client satisfaction.

Hi: Project risk management practices enhance client satisfaction.

5. MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study adopted survey research design with the aids of structured, which was used to elicit information from project managers and clients of the construction firms. The 71 building companies that are members of the Lagos Chamber of Industry and Commerce (LCCI) and their patrons are the population of this study. Krejcie and Morgan formular was employed to ascertain 57 samples of Supervisors of projects utilized the Cochran Formula to ascertain the infinite population of clients at 246. Out of the total Questionnaire sent out to the respondents, 46 and 230 was retrieved from both projects manager of the building company and its customers respectively. Most of these construction firms engages in home and business settings building. The sampling techniques for this study is multi stage, which involves stratified, random and purposive sampling techniques. Validity for this research The tool was determined using content validity, while This instrument's dependability was determined using Cronbach's alpha at $\alpha = 0.88$. Regression analysis was employed to evaluate the proposed theories using

6. RESULTS

6.1 Test of Research Hypothesis

Project risk management and project success as determined by client satisfaction do not significantly correlate.

Table 1 present the model summary of the regression result, while Tables 2 and 3 present the ANOVA result and coefficients of determination, respectively

Table 1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.580 ^a	.336	.319	.15666

a. Predictors: Project Risk Management (Constant Variable)

Table 2: ANOVA

El		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.004	1	.004	.151	.007 ^b
	Residual	1.080	44	.025		
	Total	1.084	45			

a. Dependent Variable: Clients' Satisfaction with the Company Project Risk Management Practice

b. Predictors: Project Risk Management (Constant Variable)

Table 3: coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.471	.326		13.711	.000
	Project Risk Management	.029	.074	.058	.388	.007

Dependent Variable: Clients' Satisfaction with the Company Project Risk Management Practice

The prototype synopsis (Table 1) shows that there is a strong positive association between project risk management and client satisfaction ($R = 0.580$). This suggests that when the company's project risk management gets better, client's satisfaction is also impacted. The model also illustrates how much client satisfaction variance may be explained by project risk management. The determination coefficient ($R^2 = 0.336$) shows that 33.6% Project risk management takes into consideration the variation in the degree of contentment of the client. This indicates that the contribution of project risk management to the client's satisfaction with the construction company is 33.6%.

Table 2 shows the extent to which The regression model makes predictions about the dependent variable. In other word it indicates how significant the regression model is statistically. With a p -

value of 0.007. It could be statistically inferred indicating the result variable is significantly predicted by the regression model (i.e., it is a good fit for the data).

Project risk management ($\beta_{TC} = 4.471$, $p < 0.05$) is applicable and statistically significant to predict client happiness, according to an analysis of the project's unstandardized coefficient risk control within the coefficient table (Table 3) and its corresponding p-value.

Client satisfaction = 4.471 + 0.029RM

Where, RM is risk management in the regression model

7. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study's conclusions showed a substantial correlation between client satisfaction and project risk management ($r = 0.580$; $p < 0.05$). This implies that effective Project risk management will more likely predicts result in a satisfied client. This outcome concurs with the findings of (Neriga et. al. 2012) who argue that that Managing risks is an important factor of project management in building projects. Therefore, in an effort to properly handle unforeseen circumstances and unpredictability circumstances in order to complete the project successfully. Project risk management process must remain a top priority. (Chang, et. al., 2018) also affirm think there is a noteworthy connection between project Risk control and client contentment with construction firms. Through the findings of this study, one could argue that efficient and effective project procedure for risk management could enable construction firms to identify risk, Measure and take into account risk, mitigate risk and promote policies for reducing risk. This finding also discovered that construction firms that has effective project risk management will have better financial savings, increased in productivity, better decision making and remarkable success rates in their project deliverables.

8. CONCLUSION

This study focused on relationships the connection between project client satisfaction and risk management strategies. The opinion of the project managers from the chosen building companies was obtained on their project risk control practices. Also, the same research design was used to examine the perception of their clients on their level of satisfaction as regards the project risk management practices of the construction firms. This was done in order to determine if they have any significant relationship with practices of the construction firm. The result showed that positive relationship exists between client satisfaction and project risk management techniques. A further analysis of that also revealed that construction firms that have effective project risk management will have better financial savings, increase in productivity, better decision making and success rates in their project deliverables.

The handling of project risks is a crucial component of choice -making in the building sector because clients are often significant level of danger because of the characteristics of micro and macro environments associated with construction. Therefore, in order In order to successfully and efficiently manage risk, the project manager needs to comprehend the following; risk preferences, risk responsibilities, risk event circumstances, and risk management skills.

Furthermore, risk management must become part of the strategic alignment of the organization.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Identification and management of risk should be part of an acceptable and functioning of quality and cost management strategy of the firm, based on the links between these variables as they complement each other.
2. Measures should be taken by both government and other clients to ensure that high risk projects are handled by project firms with track record of previously executed projects.
3. It is suggested that, middle and senior-level project managers be trained in the methods and risk management strategies practices. It is anticipated that the training will broaden participants' knowledge of the topic and help them appreciate how crucial risk management is to preserving project goals.

10. LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

- Client satisfaction was used as indicator to determine project success in this study, while indicators such as sales turnover, liquidity and market coverage can also be exploited in other studies

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